

Research Article

Outcomes of Core Decompression with injectable CaSO₄/CaPO₄ versus quadratus femoris muscle pedicle bone grafting for treating avascular necrosis of femoral head: A comparative study

Swapnil Ravindra Bagdure¹, Xue Jian Wu^{1*}, Peng Xiao¹, Xu Zhu¹, Chong Meng¹, Weijian Qiu¹, Yuhang Zhang¹, Zhuyao Li²

¹ Department of Orthopedics and Trauma, First Affiliated Hospital of Zhengzhou University, Zhengzhou, Henan, China

² Department of Thyroid surgery, First Affiliated Hospital of Zhengzhou University, Zhengzhou, Henan, China

***Corresponding author**

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Abstract: This study compares clinical and functional outcomes in patients with avascular necrosis of femoral head (AVNFH), treated with either autologous quadratus femoris muscle pedicle bone grafting (QF-MPBG) or core decompression combined with injectable composite graft of calcium sulfate and calcium phosphate (PRO-DENSE™). Methods: In First Affiliated Hospital of Zhengzhou University, a retrospective study from January 2015 to December 2019 included 81 patients (64 males and 17 females) diagnosed with AVNFH (IIA-IIIB), affected sides either ipsilaterally or bilaterally making a total of 100 necrotized hips. Further undergoing hip preserving surgeries, 52 patients (62 hips) underwent QF-MPBG (Control group) and 29 patients (38 hips) underwent core decompression with injectable composite graft of calcium sulfate and calcium phosphate PRO-DENSE™ (Observation group). Results: At final follow up, majority of patients in both groups showed radiological and functional improvement in hip joints. Mean Harris hip score from 68.4 and 72.4 preoperatively increased to 73.1 and 79.5 postoperatively in control and observation group respectively ($P < 0.001$). Length of incision, blood loss, operation time, hospital stays in observation group showed better results than control group ($P < 0.001$). Clinical failure includes repeated lower Harris hip score (7/38) and (9/62), collapsed joints (1/38) and (9/62), and total hip arthroplasty (1/38) and (6/62) and intertrochanteric fracture (1/38) and (0/62) in observation and control group respectively. Clinical success rate in observation group 73.6% is better than control group of 61.2%. Conclusion: This study encourages with benefits of using core decompression with injectable composite graft of calcium sulfate and calcium phosphate (PRO-DENSE™) is more suitable and preferable technique compared to autologous quadratus femoris muscle pedicle bone grafting

(QF-MPBG) for immediate treatment of AVNFH and delaying its progression and need for total hip arthroplasty in early to moderate stages.

Keywords: *Femoral head necrosis, Autologous bone graft, Core decompression, PRO-DENSE*

Abbreviations

AVNFH	Avascular necrosis of femoral head
CaSO ₄ /CaPO ₄	Calcium sulfate and Calcium phosphate
CD	Core decompression
QF-MPBG	Quadratus femoris muscle pedicle bone grafting
ARCO	Association Research Circulation Osseous
HHS	Harris Hip Score
THA	Total hip arthroplasty

Introduction

Avascular necrosis of femoral head (AVNFH) is alarming condition affecting both male and female from younger to older age of population. Femoral vessels are incompetent to maintain blood supply to intramedullary femoral head leading to necrosis, subchondral collapse and secondary osteoarthritis. Risk factors include long-term usage of corticosteroids, alcohol consumption, heavy smoking, hip traumas, idiopathic whereas obesity remains controversial ⁽¹⁻³⁾. Pain on walking with limited range of motion and abnormal gait are the chief complaint of patients presenting at the hospitals ⁽⁴⁾. Confirmatory tests include plain radiographs of pelvis and hip joints, computed tomography, and magnetic resonance imaging remains the gold standard ^(5, 6). Confirmed AVNFH is further assessed by Association Research Circulation Osseous (ARCO) staging ^(7, 8). Studies found that in delayed treatment, 70% of cases will suffer progressive joint collapse in 3 to 4 years ^(9, 10). ARCO stage II and III requires surgical interventions. Various intervention are been proposed to treat AVNFH includes core decompression with or without autologous bone grafting or injectable CaSO₄/CaPO₄ composite (PRODENSE™), vascularized or non - vascularized autologous bone grafting, proximal femoral rotational osteotomy, autologous bone marrow aspirate transplantation injectable with core decompression ⁽¹¹⁻¹⁴⁾. The hip preserving surgeries reduces the area of necrosis through extraction of necrosis bone and filling the cavity with autologous bone or synthetic bone substitutes, eventually achieving osteoconduction, osteoinduction and neovascularization hence providing a better mechanical

support and delaying the progressive deterioration which could lead to collapse of hip joint space and requiring a need for an total hip arthroplasty (THA).

None of the prior published studies have compared the clinical, radiological and functional outcomes of these two surgical interventions. Therefore, we conduct a comparative study between vascularized quadratus femoris muscle pedicle bone grafting (QF-MPBG) and core decompression with injectable composite graft of CaSO₄/CaPO₄ (PRO-DENSE™) for the treatment of AVNFB at different ARCO stages (II–III) in aiming to prevent further necrosis and deterioration of the femoral head.

Materials and Methods

Patient's evaluation

Obtaining an informed consent from 81 patients involved in retrospective study was approved by the Ethics Committee of First Affiliated Hospital of Zhengzhou University. Patients including 64 males and 17 females underwent hip preserving surgeries from January 2015 to December 2019. Total of 100 hips were confirmed for AVNFB affected moderate to late stages (ARCO IIA-IIIIB) were diagnosed using anteroposterior, frog lateral view radiographs and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI). Images were reviewed by radiologist, three senior orthopedic surgeons and 2 resident doctors. 9 hips were in stage IIA, 34 hips in stage IIB, 28 hips in stage IIC, 15 hips in stage IIIA, and 14 hips in stage IIIIB. Patients suffered from AVNFB were 32 left sided, 30 right sided and 19 were bilaterally affected [Table 1]. 29 patients (38 hips) were treated by core decompression with injectable composite graft of CaSO₄/CaPO₄ PRO-DENSE™ (Observation group) [Fig. 1]. 52 patients (62 hips) were treated by vascularized quadratus femoris muscle pedicle bone grafting (control group) [Fig. 2].

Surgical procedures

Core decompression with injectable composite graft of calcium sulfate and calcium phosphate (PRO-DENSE™)

After completing the general anesthesia, patient allowed to lie in supine position on a radiolucent table with cushion under the hip for elevation of affected side. Followed by sterile disinfection and draping. Prior to incision, a Kirschner wire was placed around imaginable position on hip

and fluoroscopic imaging was obtained to gain an overall direction and axis for drilling K wire into femoral head. Around 1.8-2.0 cm small incision was then made on the lateral side of the proximal femur from distal marking of greater trochanter followed 2.5 mm K wire was drilled into a femoral head just with 5mm beneath endosteal bony surface. 9mm cannulated drill was used to decompress the necrotic region following fluoroscopic imaging from AP and lateral views. Then a hollow cannula was placed replacing K-wire and cannulated drill. Curettage was performed to extract necrotic debris from the femoral head, and then using a specialized reamer with an expanding tip (X-REAM Percutaneous Expandable Reamer; Wright Medical Technology) was inserted and rotated with revolutions to extract a greater volume of necrotic debris. Under fluoroscopic imaging after inserting reamer, it was rotated and expanded gradually until maximum expansion at 2.1 cm deep, carefully protecting the subchondral plate and the cavity formed was then irrigated and suctioned using physiological saline. The cavity and the core tract was then backfilled with an already prepared composite graft of CaSO₄/CaPO₄ PRO-DENSE™ (Injectable Regenerative Graft; Wright Medical Technology). Beginning adequate filling from most proximal portion of the defect followed by entire cavity and core tract was confirmed under intraoperative fluoroscopy guidance. After proper irrigation and suction the incision wound are sutured by layers [Fig. 1].

Autologous quadratus femoris muscle pedicle cancellous bone grafting

After completing the general anesthesia, patient adjustments were made lying in lateral position on radiolucent table with properly elevating the operating hip. Followed by sterile disinfection and draping of affected hip. Around 8-10 cm incision was used on the posterolateral aspect of the hip. Followed by careful blunt split and retraction of gluteus maximus muscle and protecting sciatic nerve. The quadratus femoris muscle was identified along with short external rotators then divided close to their insertion. Followed by a T- shaped incision through hip capsule, the femoral neck was exposed. Close to the junction of femoral head and neck a bone window of 1.5 cm × 2.0 cm was made. The necrotic debris was removed using curettage until the cancellous bone was seen in all directions. And the cavity was further cleaned using physiological saline through repeated irrigation and suction. After finding the terminal end of the quadratus femoris muscle on the ipsilateral lower end of greater trochanter, osteotomy was made to collect the QF-MPB vascular graft. This autologous cancellous graft was then rotated and backfilled in the bony

defect of the femoral head by carefully preserving the blood vasculature and then surrounding layers of hip capsule was sutured. The drain tube was placed into the soft tissues connected outlet with negative pressured vacuum bottles and the incision was closed in layers carefully. Postoperatively the hip joint was requested to keep in the external rotatory position for about 2-3 weeks[Fig. 2].

Fig. 1 (a) Preoperative radiograph of 53 old male was alcoholic and smoker for more than 20 years shows sclerotic changes with crescent formation in bilateral femoral head, ARCO stage II B. (b) 4 weeks postoperative radiograph shows reducing the lucency and providing a structural support for femoral head. (c) 51 year old female suffered bilateral femoral head necrosis of idiopathic cause on radiograph shows subchondral degeneration and loss of contour. (d) Postoperative radiograph shows core decompression with injected CaSO₄/CaPO₄ maintaining the structural integrity of femoral head and preventing it from collapse.

Postoperative evaluation

Wound cleansing and dressings were changed on every 4th day and sutures were removed on the 12th day. After surgery from 3rd day to 6 weeks patients were allowed to begin isometric exercises on the bed and then allowed for isotonic exercises for following 6 weeks. For all the

patients radiographs were taken prior to discharge and further follow up was planned for 3 months, 6months, 1year to evaluate clinical and radiologic outcomes of patients by evaluating the Harris hip Scores (HHS) and plain radiographs or MRI scans. A clinical failure was defined by functional impairment of the limb, repeated Harris hip score lesser than 70 and radiological progression of necrotic lesion leading to abnormal femoral head contours, secondary osteoarthritis or even collapse or a need for total hip arthroplasty.

Statistical analysis

Data were analyzed using Independent T test, Mann-Whitney U test and Chi-square test under SPSS software version 22. Indicating $P < 0.05$ are statistically significant.

Fig. 2 (a) 21 year old female with SLE glomerulonephritis was treated with Prednisolone (corticosteroids) for more than 2 years, radiograph shows irregular bilateral femoral head contour with loss of subchondral bone with advanced bone degeneration ARCO stage III B. (b) Postoperative radiograph after QF-MPBG procedure shows the adequate amount of bone filling maintaining the bone density in femoral head and preventing it from further collapse allowed rest for 8 weeks and on recent follow up patient show poor HHS. (c) 37 year old male boy with 15 years history of occasional drinking with heavy smoker on radiograph shows crescent formation on bilateral femoral head with cystic and sclerotic changes staging ARCO II B. (d) After vascularized QF-MPBG radiograph showed healing process of the femoral head maintaining contour and preventing from collapse.

Results

81 patients medical data obtained from hospital records since time of admission till their last follow up, were included in this retrospective study. 29 patients (38 hips) were in observation group and 52 patients (62 hips) in control group were analyzed for mean follow up time of 27 months. Patients in observation group is comparatively older than control group ($P = 0.037$). Body mass index, gender, affected sides of hips in both groups shows no significant difference ($P > 0.05$). Preoperative Harris hip score (HHS) in observation group of 72.4 is relatively higher than control group of 68.4 ($P = 0.001$). Etiologies were chronic alcohol 38 patients, heavy smoking (more than 20 cigarettes per day) in 18 patients, long term corticosteroid use in 6 patients, 19 patients were idiopathic [Table 1]. Surgical related parameters including length of incision, blood loss, operation time and hospital stays in observation group shows better and satisfied results than control group ($P < 0.05$) [Table 2]. No patients reported any postoperative complications such as infection, hematoma, hemorrhage and non-healing of wound during their hospital stay. At final follow up, patients inside both groups were reviewed clinically by estimating mean Harris hip score higher in observation group 79.5 compared to control group 73.1. Hip survival time was calculated from the day of operation to last follow up was longer in control group than in observation group ($P < 0.001$) due to comparatively longer follow up period. Clinical failure determinants include repeated lower Harris hip scores less than 70 (7/38, 9/62), disease progression to collapsed joints (1/38, 9/62) and patients underwent total hip replacement (1/38, 6/62) in observation group, control group respectively. One patient suffered intertrochanteric fracture on 5th day following CD + CaSO₄/CaPO₄ due to early mobilization. Clinical success rate in observation group of 73.6% is higher compared to control group of 61.2% [Table 3].

Table 1 Demographic comparison of patients

Parameter	Observation group (n=38 hips)	Control group (n=62 hips)	Statistic value	P value
Age (years)	43.45±10.81	38.50±8.13	T = 2.150	P = 0.037
Body mass index (kg/m²)	24.66±1.01	24.56±1.43	T = 0.324	P = 0.747
Gender (male/female)	22/7	42/10	$\chi^2 = 0.270$	P = 0.603
Sides			Z = -1.386	P = 0.166
Left	7	25		
Right	13	17		
Bilateral	9	10		
ARCO stage			Z = -3.391	P = 0.001
IIA	9	-		
IIB	16	18		
IIC	4	25		
IIIA	6	8		
IIIB	3	11		
Preoperative HHS	72.45±5.50	68.44±4.23	T = 4.104	P = 0.001
Etiology				
Alcohol	15	23		
Smoking	7	11		
Idiopathic	5	14		
Steroid	2	4		

Table 2 Comparison of Surgical parameters

Outcome variable	Observation group (n=38)	Control group (n=62)	Statistic value	P value
Hospital stays (days)	10.4±2.56	15.2 ±4.41	T = -6.299	P = 0.001
Length of incision (cm)	2.08±0.12	10.5 ±1.63	T = -40.53	P = 0.001
Intraoperative blood loss (ml)	33.8±6.92	101.2±17.9	T = -26.53	P = 0.001
Operation time (min)	66.7±7.19	85.2 ±15.2	T = -8.189	P = 0.001

Table 3 Comparison of outcomes at final follow up

Outcome variable	Observation group (n=38)	Control group (n=62)	Statistic value	P value
Harris hip score	79.5±14.02	73.1±20.6	T = 1.794	P = 0.001
Hip survival (months)	10.14±1.94	36.62±14.89	T = -10.942	P = 0.001
Disease Progression	10	24		
Clinical success rate (%)	73.6%	61.2%		

Discussion

Postoperative clinical, radiological, surgical, and functional outcomes of patients with previous necrosis of femoral head were evaluated in this study. Observation group entitling the core decompression with injecting composite graft of calcium sulfate and calcium phosphate bone graft substitute (PRODENSE™) showed better results and also demonstrated a minimal invasive surgery with significantly improvement in the surgical trauma and achieved faster recovery in

patients. However, with some of the newer bone graft substitutes and biological bone stimulation, the success rate of these procedures may be further enhanced, and hypothesis was that a new CaSO₄/CaPO₄ composite graft, the PRO-DENSE™, could have several theoretical advantages in the mechanical support of core decompression⁽¹⁴⁾.

In order to delay the collapse of femoral head and THA, It is important to take effective and positive measures to prevent the ongoing necrosis of femoral head. Two key points must be considered. First one, the biological factor, which included removing the dead bone adequately and implanting bioactive materials to promote the bone regeneration and blood flow recovery. The other is biomechanics factor that is the bone repair material should have the function of mechanical support and osteoconduction so that it can prevent the femoral head from collapsing after the treatment^(15, 16).

When tested in pre-clinical studies, in a canine critical sized bone defect, at 13 weeks compressive strength and stiffness of restored bone was greater when bone defects were treated with the CaSO₄/CaPO₄ synthetic graft than when treated with conventional CaSO₄ pellets. Furthermore, the results seen in this canine critical defect model and aqueous dissolution testing indicate a positive multiphasic bone resorption pattern: in the early post-operative period, the CaSO₄ resorbs first through simple dissolution leaving behind an open-pore structure that allows for vascular infiltration and new bone deposition on the remaining CaPO₄ scaffold. Consequently, CD combined with injectable composite of CaSO₄/CaPO₄ bone graft substitute was widespread used to treat ONFH in recent years. Urban et al. had reported that the CaSO₄/CaPO₄ bone substitute would be gradually absorbed and replaced by new bone⁽¹⁷⁾.

The staged resorption and dense bone formation evidenced in canine studies would be desirable in core decompression techniques where healthy bony ingrowth is the goal. However it must be stressed that animal studies of bone substitute degradation cannot be transferred directly to humans⁽¹⁸⁾. The early clinical data for use with this CaSO₄/CaPO₄ composite has been encouraging. This composite has been used for benign bone tumor series and patients treated with this material reported high functional scores with low complication rates⁽¹⁹⁾.

As a result of this comparison study, we greatly reduced the length of incision, blood loss, operation time and hospital stays with the use of core decompression combined with composite

use of calcium sulfate and calcium phosphate bone graft substitute PRODENSE™. Patients were also noted a faster recovery. More importantly, in clinical results the parameters in control group were not inferior too but don't possess any great advantages as those of observation group do. After operation we can find a faster and a better quality of limb function in observation group than control group. These outcomes suggested that our minimally invasive surgery of percutaneous decompression combine CaSO₄/CaPO₄ (PRODENSE™) bone substitute had better surgical, clinical, radiological effects and significantly improved the short-term outcomes in the treatment of AVNFB.

However there are few limitations in this study. Firstly, there are only 81 patients and further there will be a need of larger sample. Secondly, observation group had a relatively shorter follow up than compared to control group and a long-term follow up study will waiting to be accomplished. According to the results of mean follow up period of 27 months, the Harris hip scores in observation group were higher than in the control group. The hip survival time in control group showed significant difference it's due to a comparatively longer follow up. The radiographic progression and clinical failure were not inferiority too. The results demonstrated that percutaneous core decompression was effective enough on removing necrotic bone and debris and provide convenient pathway to implant injectable composite of CaSO₄/CaPO₄ bone graft substitute with effective good enough short-term follow up results.

Conclusion

Core decompression combining injectable composite graft of calcium sulfate and calcium phosphate (PRODENSE™) have an excellent clinical, radiological, surgical and functional advantageous outcomes compared to autologous vascularized quadratus femoris muscle pedicle bone grafting, and can be a preferable treatment method for immediate treatment of osteonecrosis of femoral head at early and moderate stages.

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Author: Swapnil Ravindra Bagdure

MBBS at Zhengzhou University

3rd year Orthopaedics, Postgraduate student,

Zhengzhou University, Zhengzhou, Henan, China

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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